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Rare Diseases

A screening test for an earlier detection of very rare syndromes

Abstract

Who doesn't not know the situation? The waiting room is full, the physician is under pressure, yet he/she functions quite well as a doctor and has his/her knowledge and experience together. Nevertheless, some cases remain mysterious. As a result, rare diseases (orphan diseases) are still regularly diagnosed late or even way too late. As physicians who have been working on this topic for many years, we would like to provide the medical community with an experience-based quick screening test.

Warning

This questionnaire is intended for the use by fully licensed physicians only and is even in their hand in no way a substitute for any conventional diagnostic testing. No liability is taken or accepted by the authors.

RARE DISEASE EARLY DETECTION SCREENING (RDEDS)

1. Do many of your patient's symptoms match his/her medical history as well as his/her age, BMI, stature, occupation, family and professional/social history, etc.) in type and number?

IF NO: 3 POINTS

2. Is the patient complaining of persistent (single or complex) psychosomatic issues that are not tangible even with extensive laboratory testing and/or sonography, MRI, CT, PET, but is showing severe mental abnormalities such as major depression (major, pre- or postnatal, bipolar) or a psychotic episode? (Mild suspected mental diagnoses should be omitted initially and should be made by the psychiatrist if necessary).

If mood disorders do not appear medically relevant:
2 POINTS

In case of less severe symptom complexes:
3 POINTS

If moderately severe symptom complexes or even more severe:
4 POINTS

Please note:

Many rare diseases are associated with psychiatric symptoms, often even years before the "classical" systemic symptom constellations become apparent. Therefore, sudden onset psychiatric illnesses are indeed something that rare disease specialists advise, especially if a psychiatric diagnosis has manifested itself quite quickly and/or at an age of >16 years, to examine these patients thoroughly at least once a year internistically, immunologically, endocrinologically and every two years neurologically. Costs must not be an obstacle for these follow-ups. If the patient is not insured or under-insured these tests should be done at a massively reduced fee, or pro bono.

3) Does a diagnosed condition deviate from the expected course and progression?

IF YES: 2 POINTS

4. Is a new patient presenting with tangible symptoms (a kind of syndrome) whose symptoms are inconsistent with textbook knowledge?

IF YES: 3 POINTS

5) Does the patient report symptoms and disease progression that can be reconciled with standard textbook knowledge only if parts of what is described are ignored, attributed differently, or psychologized away?

IF YES: 4 POINTS

6. Does the patient frequently seek medical help because of trivialities or repetitive minor illnesses?

IF YES: 2 POINTS

7. Do laboratory tests repeatedly show abnormalities (even minimal or 'harmless' ones) that do not seem to make sense?

IF YES: 2 POINTS

8. Does the patient report symptoms or symptom complexes that at first seem implausible or even bizarre? (Example: "I am allergic to strawberries, but only if I drank coffee an hour before the reaction against strawberries.")

IF YES: 2 ½ POINTS

9. Do family members or caregivers report 'strange' symptoms that the patient himself does not address?

IF YES: 1 ½ POINTS

10. Do multiple objectifiable or credible findings exist that cannot be explained by a known widely syndrome diagnosis which has a low prevalence but is still known to most physicians?

IF YES: 2 POINTS

11. If psychologized without the most extensive somatic workup:

IF YES: 4 POINTS

12. Are there any memories that something similar has been running in the family?

IF YES: 3 ½ POINTS

EVALUATION

If a patient **scores ≥ 4 points**, he/she should be sent to an expert team of specialist for rare diseases for further tests. If a GP or any other physician should feel insecure he/she should contact an expert team for rare diseases to discuss the case without any hesitation.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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